

READING COMPREHENSION IN RELATION TO ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM

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Reading Comprehension in Relation to Academic Performance: Basis for Enhancement Program

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Abstract

This study examines the relationship between reading comprehension and academic performance in English among Grade 3 pupils at Colegio San Agustin-Bacolod during the 2023-2024 academic year. The research employs a descriptive quantitative design, utilizing standardized reading comprehension tests and academic performance records. A sample of 84 pupils were assessed across various reading skills, including letter/word recognition, phonetic analysis, reading vocabulary, and meaningful reading. The study also explores how factors such as sex, family income, and parents' educational attainment influence both reading comprehension and academic performance. Findings reveal that pupils exhibit above-average proficiency in letter/word recognition and phonetic analysis but average performance in reading vocabulary and meaningful reading. Although the overall academic performance in English is consistently outstanding across all socioeconomic groups, no statistically significant relationship was found between reading comprehension and academic performance. The results suggest that factors beyond reading comprehension, such as instructional quality and study habits, may contribute to students' success in English. The study concludes by recommending targeted interventions to enhance reading vocabulary and meaningful reading skills, alongside enrichment programs that cater to diverse learners. These strategies aim to further support the development of reading comprehension and academic excellence among Grade 3 pupils.

Keywords: *reading comprehension, academic performance, enhancement program*

Introduction

Reading comprehension is essential for academic success and lifelong learning, involving the ability to understand, interpret, and critically analyze information (Miller, 2023). It supports learning across subjects by enabling students to process and engage with material effectively, with research showing that strong comprehension skills lead to better academic performance (Francisco & Madrazo, 2019).

This skill is particularly crucial for Grade 3 pupils, who are transitioning from learning to read to reading to learn (Caraig & Quimbo, 2022). However, reading comprehension remains a concern for many Grade 3 students in the Philippines. The World Bank reports that 90% of Filipino children cannot read with comprehension, and PISA ranks the country near the bottom in reading, math, and science (O'Grady et al., 2019; Pepz, 2021). This study examines the reading comprehension skills of Grade 3 pupils at Colegio San Agustin-Bacolod and their relationship to academic performance in English. It aims to provide insights that will inform the development of a program to improve reading comprehension and academic outcomes.

Research Questions

This research aimed to determine the relationship between Reading Comprehension and the Academic Performance in English of Grade 3 learners. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of grade 3 learners when grouped according to:
 - 1.1. sex;
 - 1.2. family monthly income; and
 - 1.3. parent's educational status?
2. What is the level of reading comprehension of grade 3 pupils when taken as a whole and when grouped according to profile?
3. What is the level of reading comprehension of grade 3 pupils when grouped according to:
 - 2.1. letter/ word recognition;
 - 2.2. phonetic analysis;
 - 2.3. reading vocabulary; and
 - 2.4. meaningful reading?
4. What is the level of learners' academic performance in English as a whole and when grouped according to profile?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of Reading Comprehension Skills of Grade 3 pupils to their Academic Performance in English?
6. What enhancement program can be formulated?

Methodology

Research Design

This study aimed to assess the relationship between the Reading Comprehension and Academic Performance in English of Grade 3

Pupils of Colegio San Agustin Bacolod, Academic Year 2023-2024. Thus, the researcher used descriptive quantitative research design. Descriptive quantitative research is used to obtain information to describe a phenomenon, situation, or population. More specifically, it helps answer the what, when, where, and how questions regarding the research problem rather than the why.

It aims to describe the characteristics, behaviors, or attitudes of a population or phenomenon. It quantifies variables of interest without trying to infer causal relationships. It involves collecting numerical data and analyzing it statistically. Researchers do not manipulate variables. They observe and measure them as they naturally occur (Sahoo & Behera, 2019).

Respondents

The subject and respondents of the study is the Grade 3 pupils of Colegio San Agustin – Bacolod enrolled in the Academic Year 2023-2024. The researcher utilized a population of Grade 3 learners, totaling 84 respondents. The present study used the population therefore, there was no sample technique employed.

Instrument

This study aimed to assess the reading comprehension skills of Grade 3 learners using a comprehensive data-gathering instrument that consisted of two parts. The first component was a questionnaire designed to gather demographic information about the pupils, while the second component utilized the Gray Diagnostic Reading Tests (GDRT), a standardized assessment tool created by William S. Gray. The GDRT evaluated various aspects of reading ability, including decoding, fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension, making it an effective means to identify reading difficulties and assess skill levels. By analyzing the results of the GDRT, educators could tailor their instructional strategies to meet the specific needs of each learner.

The researcher gathered the results of the Gray Diagnostic Reading Test (GDRT) of Grade 3 learners, with particular emphasis on their performance in letter and word recognition, phonetic analysis, reading vocabulary, and meaningful reading. These components were used to assess the learners' overall reading comprehension ability. The reading comprehension scores were then compared with their academic grades in the English subject, as well as their individual profiles, to analyze potential correlations and insights. Additionally, a focus interview with teachers was conducted to develop targeted recommendations for interventions aimed at enhancing students' reading skills.

Procedure

The researcher first sought approval from the school's President and the Principal of the Basic Education Department. Afterwards, consent was obtained from parents to gather information such as their educational attainment and monthly income, along with the level of reading comprehension skills of Grade 3 learners from the BED Guidance Office. Next, the researcher collected data on academic performance from the BED Academic Coordinator, ensuring alignment with a standardized grading system widely recognized in educational contexts. The gathered data was then utilized in this research. Finally, a focus interview was conducted to formulate recommendations as part of possible interventions to improve and enhance the reading skills of the pupils.

Data Analysis

After gathering the data, the researcher tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted the results. Different statistical tools were used in the analysis and interpretation of data.

To address Statement of the Problem No. 1, which pertains to the profile of Grade 3 learners categorized by (a) sex, (b) family monthly income, and (c) parents' educational status, frequency and percentage distribution were employed.

To answer Statement of the Problem No. 2, regarding the level of reading comprehension of Grade 3 pupils in terms of (a) letter/word recognition, (b) phonetic analysis, (c) reading vocabulary, and (d) meaningful reading, the mean was used, with an interpretation guide from the school's Guidance and Testing Center.

For Statement of the Problem No. 3, which examines the level of reading comprehension of Grade 3 pupils both as a whole and when grouped according to their profile, the mean was applied, following the DepEd grading system.

To answer the statement of the problem no. 4, what is the level of learners' academic performance in English, mean and standard deviation was used.

To address Statement of the Problem No. 5, which explores whether there is a significant relationship between the level of reading comprehension skills of Grade 3 pupils and their academic performance in English, correlation analysis (Pearson's correlation coefficient) was utilized.

Lastly, to answer Statement of the Problem No. 6, which involves formulating an enhancement program, the researcher conducted a focus interview with selected English teachers and the area coordinator. This interview aided in the development of an enhancement program based on the study's results, with the discussion presented in the recommendation section of the research paper.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data, analyses, interpretations, and discussions related to the study. The data were organized and displayed in tabular form, following the sequence of the specific problems addressed in the research.

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

There were 84 respondents in this study. Table 1 presents the profile of the Grade 3 learners when grouped according to sex, family income, and parental educational attainment.

Table 1. *Frequency and Percent Distribution of Grade 3 Learners' Profile*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Sex	Male	38	45.20
	Female	46	54.80
	Total	84	100.00
Family Income	Low-income but not poor	1	1.20
	Lower Middle	14	16.70
	Middle	10	11.90
	Upper Middle	49	58.30
	Upper Middle but not rich	4	4.80
	Rich	6	7.10
	Total	84	100.00
Mother's Educational Attainment	College Level	3	3.60
	College Graduate	77	91.70
	Doctoral Degree	2	2.40
	Vocational Graduate	1	1.20
	Undergraduate	1	1.20
	Total	84	100.00
Father's Educational Attainment	Elementary Graduate	1	1.20
	College Level	1	1.20
	College Graduate	80	95.20
	N/A	2	2.40
	Total	84	100.00

The profile of the Grade 3 respondents, as detailed in Table 1, shows a balanced distribution in terms of sex, with 45.2 percent of the respondents being male (38 pupils) and 54.8 percent being female (46 pupils), totaling 84 respondents.

Regarding family income, most of the respondents come from upper middle-income families, accounting for 58.3 percent (49 families). A smaller percentage, 16.7 percent (14 families), are from lower middle-income families, and 11.9 percent (10 families) are categorized as middle income. Additionally, 7.1 percent (6 families) of the respondents are from rich families, while 4.8 percent (4 families) are from upper middle-income families that are not rich. A very small portion, 1.2 percent (1 family), falls into the low-income but not poor category.

In terms of the mothers' educational attainment, a significant majority of the respondents' mothers, 91.7 percent (77 individuals), are college graduates. A smaller percentage have mothers with a college-level education without a degree (3.6 percent, 3 individuals). A minority of the respondents have mothers with a doctoral degree (2.4 percent, 2 individuals), vocational graduate (1.2 percent, 1 individual), or some undergraduate education (1.2 percent, 1 individual).

Similarly, the fathers' educational attainment is predominantly high, with 95.2 percent (80 individuals) being college graduates. Additionally, 1.2 percent (1 individual) of the respondents have fathers who graduated from elementary school, and another 1.2 percent (1 individual) have fathers with some college education but no degree. For 2.4 percent (2 individuals) of the respondents, the fathers' educational attainment was either not applicable or not recorded.

Overall, the profile indicates that the Grade 3 respondents primarily come from families with middle to upper middle-income levels, and their parents, particularly the mothers, exhibit a high level of educational attainment, mostly being college graduates.

Level of Reading Comprehension in Terms of Profile

The table below shows the level of reading comprehension of Grade 3 pupils when taken as a whole and when grouped according to profile.

In terms of sex as a profile, both males and females exhibit above-average reading comprehension levels. Males (38 pupils) have a mean score of 115.13, while females (46 pupils) have a slightly higher mean score of 117.89.

Table 2. *Level of Reading Comprehension when taken as a whole and when grouped according to Profile*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Sex	Male	38	115.13	Above average
	Female	46	117.89	Above average
Family Income	Low-income but not poor	1	102	Average
	Lower Middle	14	114.29	Above average
	Middle	10	124.4	Superior
	Upper Middle	49	115.76	Above average
	Upper Middle but not rich	4	119.25	Above average
	Rich	6	117.17	Above average
Mother's Educational Attainment	College Level	3	118.33	Above average
	College Graduate	77	116.79	Above average
	Doctoral Degree	2	123.5	Superior
	Vocational Graduate	1	103	Average
Father's Educational Attainment	Undergraduate	1	100	Average
	Elementary Graduate	1	100	Average
	College Level	1	128	Superior
	College Graduate	80	116.84	Above average
	N/A	2	111.5	Above average
As a whole		84	116.64	Above average

In terms of family income, the pupils from different economic backgrounds show varying levels of reading comprehension. Pupils from low-income but not poor families (1 pupil) have an average comprehension level with a mean score of 102. Those from lower-middle-income families (14 pupils) have above-average comprehension levels with a mean score of 114.29. Pupils from middle-income families (10 pupils) have a superior comprehension level with a mean score of 124.4. Upper-middle-income families (49 pupils) and upper-middle but not rich families (4 pupils) both show above-average comprehension levels with mean scores of 115.76 and 119.25, respectively. Pupils from rich families (6 pupils) also demonstrate above-average comprehension levels with a mean score of 117.17.

Mother's educational attainment appears to influence reading comprehension significantly. Pupils whose mothers have a college-level education (3 pupils) have above-average comprehension levels with a mean score of 118.33. Those whose mothers are college graduates (77 pupils) also have above-average comprehension levels, with a mean score of 116.79. Pupils whose mothers hold doctoral degrees (2 pupils) have superior comprehension levels with a mean score of 123.5.

Father's educational attainment shows a similar trend. Pupils whose fathers have college-level education (1 pupil) exhibit superior comprehension levels with a mean score of 128. Those whose fathers are college graduates (80 pupils) have above-average comprehension levels with a mean score of 116.84. Pupils whose fathers have vocational degrees (1 pupil) or undergraduate degrees (1 pupil) show average comprehension levels with mean scores of 103 and 100, respectively. Those whose fathers have elementary education (1 pupil) also have an average comprehension level with a mean score of 100.

Overall, the reading comprehension level for the entire group of 84 pupils is above average, with a mean score of 116.64. The study reveals that both males and females exhibit above-average reading comprehension levels, with females slightly outperforming males. This supports the study of Skelton & Valentine (2021), which provides an updated analysis of gender differences in reading achievement in the United States, reinforcing the finding that females often outperform males in reading comprehension, with a focus on recent data and trends.

Additionally, pupils from higher-income families and those with parents who have higher educational attainment generally have better reading comprehension. This is consistent with the study of McCoy & Raver (2020), which found that family income remains a significant factor influencing children's academic performance, including reading comprehension. It underscores the persistence of income-related disparities in educational outcomes, despite various interventions.

Furthermore, this finding also supports the study of Choi & Kim (2022), which highlights that higher levels of parental education positively influence the academic achievements of learners, including reading comprehension.

Level of Reading Comprehension in Terms of Reading Components

The table below shows the level of reading comprehension of Grade 3 pupils when taken as a whole and when grouped according to letter/word recognition, phonetic analysis, reading vocabulary, and meaningful reading.

The table presents the level of reading comprehension among Grade 3 pupils, broken down into four specific reading components: letter/word recognition, phonetic analysis, reading vocabulary, and meaningful reading. Each component's level of engagement is assessed with a mean score derived from a sample size (n) of 84 students.

Table 3. *Level of Reading Comprehension of Grade 3 Learners*

<i>Level of Engagement</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Letter/ word recognition	84	13.82	Above average
Phonetic Analysis	84	12.67	Above Average
Reading Vocabulary	84	11.94	Average
Meaningful Reading	84	11.02	Average

The finding reveals that pupils exhibit above-average proficiency in letter/word recognition and phonetic analysis, with mean scores of 13.82 and 12.67, respectively. In contrast, their performance in reading vocabulary and meaningful reading is average, as indicated by mean scores of 11.94 and 11.02.

The study by Kiew and Shah (2020) supports the findings of this study by emphasizing the crucial role of vocabulary knowledge in reading comprehension. If pupils in this research have low reading vocabulary, it suggests that they may struggle more with reading comprehension due to insufficient word recognition skills. This underscores the importance of implementing instruction in reading, spelling, and vocabulary to enhance word awareness and help students become independent word-solvers, ultimately improving their reading comprehension skills. Thus, addressing vocabulary deficits could be key to improving overall reading performance in student population.

Level of Academic Performance of learners in English as a whole and when grouped according to Profile Variables

Analyzing the academic performance of Grade 3 pupils provides essential insights for educational planning and support. This analysis assesses overall academic achievement and further breaks it down based on profile characteristics such as gender, monthly income of parents, and educational level. The table below provides a quick summary of the pupils' academic performance.

Table 4. *Level of Academic Performance of Grade 3 learners in English when taken as whole and when grouped according to profile*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Sex	Male	38	93.43	Outstanding
	Female	46	94.01	Outstanding
Family Income	Low-income but not poor	1	90.25	Outstanding
	Lower Middle	14	93.50	Outstanding
	Middle	10	95.33	Outstanding
	Upper Middle	49	93.66	Outstanding
	Upper Middle but not rich	4	93.56	Outstanding
	Rich	6	93.17	Outstanding
Mother's Educational Attainment	College Level	3	95.58	Outstanding
	College Graduate	77	93.67	Outstanding
	Doctoral Degree	2	95.00	Outstanding
	Vocational Graduate	1	93.00	Outstanding
Father's Educational Attainment	Undergraduate	1	92.75	Outstanding
	Elementary Graduate	1	92.75	Outstanding
	College Level	1	94.50	Outstanding
	College Graduate	80	93.76	Outstanding
	N/A	2	93.38	Outstanding
	As a whole	84	93.75	Outstanding

The table illustrates the English academic performance levels of Grade 3 pupils, categorized by sex, parents' monthly income, and educational attainment. The results, interpreted based on average scores, reveal consistently high performance across all groups.

Among females, the mean score is 94.01, which is classified as "Outstanding." Similarly, males achieve a mean score of 93.43, also rated as "Outstanding."

When examining family income, pupils from families considered poor (1 family) have an average score of 90.25, interpreted as "Outstanding." This high level of performance continues as we move to higher social status. Pupils from lower-middle status (14 families) score an average of 93.50, while those in the middle status (10 families) achieve an even higher mean score of 95.33. For upper middle (49 families), the mean score is 93.66, and for those with upper middle status (4 families), the score is 93.5625. Even in the highest economic status which rich (6 families), the mean score remains impressive at 93.1667. All these scores are categorized as "Outstanding."

Overall, when considering the academic performance of all groups collectively, the mean score is 93.7500, which is classified as "Outstanding."

In terms of the educational attainment of parents. For mothers, pupils whose mothers are college undergraduates have a mean score of 92.75, while those with college graduate mothers have a mean score of 93.67. Pupils with mothers who are vocational graduates score an average of 93.00, and those with postgraduate mothers achieve a mean score of 95.00. Overall, the mean score for all categories combined is 93.75.

For the educational attainment of fathers, pupils with elementary graduate fathers have a mean score of 92.75, while those with college graduate fathers have a mean score of 94.50. Pupils whose fathers fall into the "Others" category achieve a mean score of 93.38. The overall mean score for all categories is also 93.75. Across all categories and educational levels, the academic performance of learners is consistently interpreted as "Outstanding."

The findings suggest that the Grade 3 pupils consistently achieve high levels of academic performance in English, regardless of sex, parents' monthly income, or parents' educational attainment. The uniformly "Outstanding" scores across all categories indicate that various socioeconomic factors and educational backgrounds of parents do not significantly impact the English academic performance of learners. This consistent excellence could imply a strong, supportive educational environment or effective teaching methods that enable all students to excel.

Research supports these findings by highlighting the complex interplay between parental income, education, and the academic outcomes of learners. For instance, Davis-Kean, Tighe, and Waters (2021) in *Current Directions in Psychological Science* emphasize that higher parental educational attainment positively influences both parenting practices and the development of learners. Their study finds that parents with higher education levels engage in more effective parenting strategies, which are associated with better academic and developmental outcomes for children. This supports the indication in the table that the high performance of learners remains consistent across different parental education levels.

Additionally, Cooper and Stewart (2021) conducted a systematic review published in *Child Indicators Research* that found a significant association between household income and children's outcomes. Their review reveals that higher household income is linked to better academic performance, improved health, and enhanced social-emotional development in children. The study underscores that increased income provides access to better educational resources and reduces stress, which positively affects child development. This aligns with the findings in the table, suggesting that the school environment or teaching methods might be robust enough to mitigate the typical disparities caused by socioeconomic factors, contributing to uniformly high academic performance among all students.

Relationship between Reading Comprehension and Academic Performance

The table reveals the relationship between the level of reading comprehension and academic performance in English of Grade 3 pupils for School Year 2023-2024.

Table 5. *Relationship between the Level of Reading Comprehension and Academic Performance in English of Grade 3 Pupils*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Reading Comprehension Skills	84	116.64
Academic Performance	84	93.75

Computed Value (r): 0.17

P-value: 0.115

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

When taken as a whole, the mean score for reading comprehension skills is 116.64, while the mean score for academic performance is 93.75. The computed correlation coefficient (r) is 0.17, indicating a weak positive relationship between reading comprehension skills and academic performance. However, the p -value is 0.115, which is greater than the significance level of 0.05. As a result, the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted, suggesting that there is no statistically significant relationship between reading comprehension and academic performance in English of Grade 3 pupils of the Basic Education Department of Colegio San Agustin-Bacolod at the 0.05 level of significance.

This is consistent with the findings of Stoffelsma and De Jong (2019), who found no significant direct link between English reading proficiency and academic performance among university students in Ghana, suggesting that other factors, such as teaching quality and language barriers, might also influence academic outcomes.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this research study, the following conclusions were reached:

Most Grade 3 pupils at the Basic Education Department of Colegio San Agustin-Bacolod come from upper-middle-class families, with many parents being college graduates. This likely provides students with resources and support that enhance their education. Overall, Grade 3 pupils have above-average reading comprehension levels, suggesting that the school's reading programs and teaching methods are effective. However, differences based on sex, family income, and parents' education indicate that these factors may influence reading comprehension.

Students show strong skills in letter/word recognition and phonetic analysis, but their performance in reading vocabulary and meaningful reading is average. This highlights the need for targeted support in these areas to improve their vocabulary and comprehension. Grade 3 pupils excel in English across all categories, reflecting the effectiveness of the school's English curriculum and teaching methods, as shown by a high mean score. The lack of a significant relationship between reading comprehension and academic performance in English suggests that other factors, such as teaching methods, study habits, and additional skills, may also contribute to the students' success in English.

Based on the findings and conclusions mentioned earlier, the following recommendations are proposed:

Since Grade 3 pupils demonstrate average performance in reading vocabulary and meaningful reading, additional support can be provided in these areas. Teachers can incorporate vocabulary-building activities, such as word games, context-based exercises, and interactive reading sessions, to help expand the vocabulary of learners and improve their ability to understand and use words in various contexts. Given the variations in reading comprehension based on sex, family income, and educational attainment of parents, targeted interventions can be implemented for groups that may require additional support. For example, extra reading sessions, personalized tutoring, or group activities can be offered to students from lower-income backgrounds or those with less parental educational support to ensure equitable academic development.

While students excel in letter/word recognition and phonetic analysis, there is a need to enhance their ability to comprehend and derive meaning from texts. Incorporating activities that focus on reading comprehension, such as discussion-based reading groups, critical thinking exercises, and narrative-building tasks, can foster a deeper understanding of the texts they read. To further improve reading comprehension, ongoing assessments can be conducted to track the progress of students, particularly in areas of vocabulary and meaningful reading. Teachers can use formative assessments, quizzes, and student reflections to evaluate the growth of learners and provide timely feedback for improvement.

Given the lack of a significant relationship between reading comprehension and academic performance in English, it is important to acknowledge that success in English is likely influenced by various factors, including study habits, motivation, and other skills. Encouraging students to develop strong study routines, offering extracurricular English activities, and fostering an environment that promotes language use both inside and outside the classroom can contribute to enhanced academic performance. As parental educational attainment plays a role in the performance of learners, schools can engage parents in the learning process through workshops, regular communication, and involvement in school activities. Encouraging parents to create a supportive learning environment at home can help reinforce the academic efforts of the school.

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